

Corrigendum: Checklist of the Phoridae (Diptera, Aschiza) of the Balkan Peninsula countries

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This corrects the article “Checklist of the Phoridae (Diptera, Aschiza) of the Balkan Peninsula countries”, volume 48: pp. 15–37.

On page 21, column 1, line 9; page 25, column 1, line 48; page 25, column 2, lines 15, 19; page 26, column 1, lines 39, 45, 47; page 26, column 2, lines 28, 29; page 29, column 2, lines 18, 22 – Schmitz, 1957a to be replaced with Schmitz, 1957.

On page 28, column 2, line 24 – Schmitz, 1957b to be replaced with Schmitz, 1957.

On page 22, column 1, line 35; page 26, column 1, line 34; page 30, column 1, lines 11, 14, 17 – Schmitz, 1958a to be replaced with Schmitz, 1958.

The bibliographic sources for citations Schmitz, 1957; Schmitz, 1958; Schmitz & Beyer, 1965a; Schmitz & Beyer, 1965b; Schmitz & Beyer, 1974; Schmitz & Delage, 1974; Schmitz & Delage, 1981 have been omitted in the “References” section; added here.

Schmitz H. 1958 33. Phoridae. In: Lindner E. (ed.) Die Fliegen der palaearktischen Region 4 (7) Lief. 202: 465–512.

Schmitz H., Beyer E.M. 1965a 33. Phoridae. In: Lindner E. (ed.) Die Fliegen der palaearktischen Region 4 (7) Lief. 258: 513–560.

Schmitz H., Beyer E.M. 1965b 33. Phoridae. In: Lindner E. (ed.) Die Fliegen der palaearktischen Region 4 (7) Lief. 260: 561–608.

Schmitz H., Beyer E.M. 1974 33. Phoridae. In: Lindner E. (ed.) Die Fliegen der palaearktischen Region 4 (7) Lief. 301: 609–637.

Schmitz H., Delage A. 1974 33. Phoridae. In: Lindner E. (ed.) Die Fliegen der palaearktischen Region 4 (7) Lief. 301: 638–664.

Schmitz H., Delage A. 1981 33. Phoridae. In: Lindner E. (ed.) Die Fliegen der palaearktischen Region 4 (7) Lief. 325: 665–712.

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